

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D3.1 – Publication of generic guidelines for the organization of topic-specific Open Calls

WP3 – Demonstrators and Open Calls for User Projects
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Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Project Objectives	3
Detailed Report on the Deliverable.....	4
1. Background	4
2. Description of Work.....	4
3. Next steps	14
Abbreviations	14
Delivery and Schedule.....	15

Executive Summary

The EOSC-Life project aims to integrate data resources and data processing workflows developed by and in collaboration with the Life Science Research Infrastructures (LS RIs) in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This Work Package, WP3, has the objective to identify scientific user projects that will drive this integration and that will allow the scientific community to shape the building of the EOSC for the life sciences by expressing their needs, and by feeding in their requirements.

With this document, WP3 presents the guidelines on the preparation, organization and framework of Open Calls for User Projects that will be the main tool for the identification of suitable projects. The Open Calls are designed to contribute to achieving the overarching goal of WP3: to enable EOSC-empowered ground-breaking research, and to generate new knowledge by linking the life science communities to a variety of data resources and a platform of various data analysis tools. By identifying and selecting suitable user projects, WP3 will take a pragmatic approach for populating as well as developing solutions and testing of the EOSC for life sciences. Reusing FAIR data resources and having workflows run in the cloud is becoming increasingly important for researchers, however, building and spreading of cloud technology related skills is still needed for many researchers. WP3 will address those scientists via Open Calls by offering applicants training and consultation with experts across the EOSC-Life consortium. By providing funding, WP3 will also empower scientific groups that have built the capacity and skill sets to run their projects mostly independently or in collaboration. Importantly, selected projects are expected to have a lasting impact and to leave behind some legacy, so that future projects can benefit from their work and re-use their data, tools or workflows. Projects should present novelty in terms of the interplay between RIs and the EOSC, and address important challenges and needs of the life science community.

Project Objectives

The general objective of this work package is to identify data resources and data analysis workflows relevant to the Life Science communities and providing a fast, coordinated and user-oriented way to connect the LS RIs to EOSC via selected use cases. Actual scientific and technological projects representing a broad scope of different domains in the Life Sciences will be selected to guide and structure the work in order to allow implementation of processes with concrete exemplary projects at hand.

With this deliverable, the project has reached the following objective:

- 1) Develop practical guidelines based on the experience with the initial set of demonstrators to inform the organization of topic-specific Open Calls

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Background

WP3 has been supporting user projects from Day 1 of EOSC-Life through our so-called Demonstrator Projects. Demonstrator projects were pre-selected from life science research infrastructures (LS RIs) participating in the EOSC-Life project consortium during the grant writing phase. This approach enabled the consortium to start working on concrete, tangible use cases straight from the start of the project. It has also helped to identify some critical issues in enabling and supporting these types of data- and workflow-heavy scientific projects. Nevertheless, the EOSC for the Life Sciences should be shaped and informed not only by the 'closed club' of LS RIs, but should also meet the expectation of the broader scientific community. For this reason, WP3 organizes publicly advertised, peer-reviewed Open Calls that support an unbiased selection process to allow contribution and participation also by outsiders of this consortium.

The initial plan in WP3 was to launch Open Calls (OC) with predefined topics as described in the grant proposal in our Description of Work. One OC was supposed to cover the topic of AI/Machine learning (OC1) with a special emphasis on attracting users from the industrial sector. The 2nd Open Call (OC2) was supposed to address the research community working with sensitive data in medical research (patient data) or with classified data (BSL3 containment related data, IP-protected data) and a final Open Call (OC3) was supposed to accept applications from various life science fields, driven by user needs without a predetermined thematic orientation. Please see the appendix for a more detailed description. In 2.2, we will describe the changes that were implemented to this initial plan and outline the strategic approach taken that motivated those adaptations.

2. Description of Work

2.1. Open Call – Structure

WP3 will organize up to three Open Calls (OC) for user projects starting in year 2 of EOSC-Life, which are led by dedicated Open Call Leads and which will target different scientific themes.

All OCs are expected to follow the OC guidelines laid out in this deliverable D3.1. All preparatory work leading up to the launch of the first OC is supported by the group of nominated Open Call Leads. The individual OCs are then supported specifically by their leads, who act as main contact persons. OC leads will provide appropriate support in the role of a project manager, managing the application process and driving and ensuring project progress. In the following, this document will specify aspects common to all Open Calls such as selection criteria, evaluation procedures and different support models for OC projects.

WP3 aims to select between 9 – 12 projects in total across all Open Calls, depending on duration, scope and requested resources. The number of projects per Open Call will not be predetermined, but will depend on the number of requests and the quality of the submitted proposals. The first Open Call should accept a maximum of 8 projects.

2.2. Open Call – Determining Scope

2.2.1. Market research

During project-internal discussions (e.g. at the EOSC-Life retreat and during meetings among WP1, WP2 and WP3), the concern was expressed that the technical expertise currently available across the consortium was not necessarily in line with the predefined topics for the Open Calls. Furthermore, the question arose whether those topics were indeed addressing the most urgent needs in our user community. As we wanted to ensure that the WP3 Open Calls meet the expectations of the scientists working in the different scientific areas our 13 LS RIs are connected to and that they indeed help to populate and thereby shape the EOSC in a way it is useful for the community, we conducted some market research. This market research had the purpose to prepare and construct the OCs in such a way that their impact is maximized, ensuring that the right topics are selected and that the timing of their launch is in accordance with both support capacity across the consortium as well as user readiness to submit relevant proposals. The market research was defined as an internal scoping exercise addressed to all LS RIs participating in EOSC-Life and it should inform us of the areas of special interest to communities associated with our RIs.

Responses to our market research enabled us to gain an overview of the variety of projects foreseen and to assess the readiness of our potential applicants to engage with us through the Open Calls. In total, the market research resulted in the submission of 29 project ideas, which was quite a remarkable figure considering that we only distributed this request internally across the consortium. Submitted project ideas were assigned to the different pre-identified Open Call topics by the Open Call Leads. Project ideas were assigned to “AI/Machine learning”, “Sensitive data”, “Industry” or “General” when the project did not align with one of the other pre-identified topics. Once topics had been assigned we asked WP1 and WP2 Leads to provide feedback (based on the limited information provided per project idea) to which extent they would consider these projects as feasible and in line with their own WP objectives.

From our analysis 15 projects fell into the category "General", 12 into the category "sensitive data", two projects were classified as "AI and Machine learning" and none came from the industrial sector. Therefore, the decision was taken to be as open and welcoming as possible in the 1st Open Call, allowing all scientists to submit their proposals by making the 1st Open Call the ‘general’ one, i.e. not specifying the topic any further and thereby capturing the largest share of the submitted project ideas.

Notably, the evaluation by WP1 and WP2 revealed an overall positive picture, as many projects were rated as feasible (20 projects for WP1 and 15 projects for WP2), and the remaining projects were often not requesting the services of the respective WPs or the information provided was not sufficient for a clear categorization. For the market research exercise the level of detail we requested from participants to submit a project idea was kept to a minimum to

keep the ‘entry barrier’ low. Consequently the technical evaluations were only performed on a very high and general level.

In this current guideline document, we advise that the results of the market research are also considered when selecting the topics for the future Open Calls. We recommend to not confirm the topics for all future Open Calls at this stage, and instead to retain the flexibility to take upcoming developments into account. It was noted, for example, that some project ideas (6 in total) involved project consortia which are already established. Prioritizing such applications could increase the potential impact by exploiting synergies across projects.

On the other hand, the lack of project ideas coming from the industrial sector should not be interpreted as lack of interest, but can be assigned to the fact that the market research was an internal exercise only and did not reach out to companies and SMEs to collect their ideas. Based on personal communication and input provided by Industry Liaison Officers we believe that the industrial sector is, on the contrary, highly interested in working together with EOSC-Life.

2.2.2. Response to Covid-19

EOSC-Life is committed to assisting with research efforts targeting SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19. Within the WP3 Open Calls scientific projects on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 would be automatically eligible to apply to the 1st and general Open Call, but they may also be prioritized compared to other projects, if their relevance is striking and if there is an urgent need to start working on them as soon as possible by evaluating such proposals before the final call deadline. Also in the Open Calls that will follow at a later time point, we would recommend that research on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 will still be eligible and prioritized, irrespective of the actual call topic.

2.3. Open Call – Service, Assistance and Training offer

2.3.1. General Support offering

The definition of ‘services’ or ‘support functions’ offered to OC projects is not trivial in the context of EOSC-Life. The service providing entity is not an institute or a core facility, but it is the EOSC-Life WP, and usually only a subset of its WP participants. This requires a lot of coordination within the WP and a clear definition of what the technical experts can offer as service or support to user projects. Clear statements are needed from the applicants on their requirements. These requirements must be aligned with the support available from the technical experts. During the application process, the user will be asked to define the application area in different categories that are aligned to the tasks of the supporting WPs (such as e.g. Data curation, handling and integration for publishing into the cloud (WP1), Tool interoperability, workflows and containerisation (WP2), Cloud deployment and resources (WP7)).

After detailed discussion within the individual WPs and across WPs, the technical experts in WP1, WP2 and WP7 will provide the projects applying in the WP3 OC with expert consultation during the project preparation phase (described below) as well as training during the project kick-off phase and in some limited cases also technical support as far as capacity exists within the respective WPs and alignment of the projects to the WP’s own goals. We will also welcome projects that can operate independently, by bringing in sufficient expertise themselves. Those

projects can benefit in EOSC-Life Open Calls from resources to run their project and from access to training opportunities such as workshops, hackathons or webinars. For applicants external to the RI ecosystem, the EOSC-Life Open Calls will give them the opportunity to connect with relevant research infrastructures which can assist them in exploitation, visibility and sustainability of their project results. In either case, it is of critical importance to provide detailed information on the expected benefits for applicants to ensure sufficient attractiveness of the Open Call.

WP3 has coordinated the development of the proposal application form¹, using the WP1 call application form as a starting point² and integrating WP2-specific fields and relevant fields from the WP7 Resource Allocation Process. WP1/2/7 were invited to provide feedback and to further refine their support offering and the applicant questionnaire, taking into account their experience with the first generation of demonstrator projects. The final application form is accessible via ARIA³ and the EOSC-Life document gallery⁴, so that users can familiarise themselves with the proposal form ahead of submission.

As WP1/2/7 will be involved in the evaluation process itself (described below), our approach ensures that the support requested will match the support available and that the selection of Open Call projects is well aligned with WP-internal policies (as e.g. the Resource Allocation Process in WP7 and the WP2 Roadmap⁵). If applicants are not requesting direct support from the WPs, but prefer to work self-sustainably within their own team, the technical evaluation is expected to focus on the general alignment of the proposed project with EOSC-Life objectives.

2.3.2. Expert consultation during the maturation phase

Consultation with the technical experts from WP1, WP2 and WP7 is a key step in the maturation phase of the project proposals and will be encouraged in the application user interface with clear buttons/links to contact the relevant experts from the technical work packages.

Here, we describe the scenario for a typical project:

1. Applicant selects area of technical alignment of their projects and makes contact with the technical work package experts via the WP3 OC leads using the contact buttons
2. The WP3 Lead/OC Leads team will check the technical alignment of the project with WP1, 2 and/or 7 and forward the applicants request to the respective WP leads.
3. Each technical work package contacted will assign an expert to the proposal under development to discuss requirements of the applicants and align these with the capacity of the WP, bring in technical perspectives, and provide feedback on the proposal to help the applicants to refine the project plan.
4. After the consultation the applicant team submit their proposal in ARIA before the deadline.
5. In the application form users will be asked to confirm that they have been in contact with the technical experts to discuss their project and specify who that expert was.

¹ <https://instruct-eric.eu/submit-proposal/?t=eosclife>

² <https://www.eosc-life.eu/services/cloud-data-deployment-call/>

³ <https://instruct-eric.eu/submit-proposal/?t=eosclife>

⁴ <http://eosc-life.eu/opencall>

⁵ <https://forum.eosc-life.eu/t/eosc-life-wp2-roadmap/31>

6. The expert involved in the consultation is advised to provide the technical evaluation of the submitted proposal.
7. If the project is selected, this technical expert might continue to provide technical expertise to the project team if needed.

2.4. Open Call – Timeline

WP3 Leads aim to launch the first OC (OC1) in September 2020 (M19). At the moment, no clear prediction is made on potential start dates for OC2 and OC3, as topics and timing will be determined based on user community interest in the first Open Call, and further developments in the project. However, we recommend that OCs should all be launched before M26 of the project to allow sufficient time for user project completion.

Each Open Call will be open for submissions for 3 months. All submitted proposals will be evaluated in parallel once the deadline has passed to encourage competition and allow prioritization. Before submitting their application, applicants will have to contact the experts for each of the areas of support they are requesting, or, if they are not requesting technical support from EOSC-Life, for each of the areas their project is aligned with. An expert will then be assigned to their proposal under development to discuss their requirements and align these with the available resources in their WP, bring in technical perspectives, and provide feedback on the proposal to help the applicant to refine the proposal. We expect that this “maturation phase” will increase the focus and impact of submitted projects. Contact between the applicant and the technical expert will be made within the ARIA application system and first mediated by the WP3 Leads and OC Leads to assign the project to WP1, WP2 and/or WP7. The assignment of the experts within the respective WP will be done by their WP leads.

The later OCs can run in parallel, but the availability of technical experts has to be taken into consideration. As Demonstrator projects are expected to come to an end by M20, overlap between those projects and approved OC projects will be minimal, which should help to keep the workload under control. Nevertheless, it will be critical to monitor available capacity closely and match human resources both to new and ongoing projects and to potentially prioritize in future Open Calls those projects that bring in the necessary skill set themselves.

2.5. Open Call – Application Management

User projects will be managed via ARIA, the application management system developed by Instruct-ERIC, which has been extensively tested and refined for use by multiple RIs via the CORBEL Open Calls⁶. EOSC-Life WP1 and WP9 also used ARIA for the management of their calls, and this consistency will support acceptance and familiarity of this management system across the consortium.

⁶ <https://www.corbel-project.eu/about-corbel/open-call.html>

Figure 1: Open Call application process in ARIA

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Each call will be managed by the respective Open Call leads, i.e. they would assume the role of a ‘moderator’ in ARIA. When necessary, WP3 Leads can provide additional support. Consortium members that will take an active role in the evaluation of proposals (see below) are expected to create an ARIA account to submit their evaluation. Within ARIA, the ‘Access’ functionality will be used, which allows for independent scientific peer-review and technical reviews steps to be conducted. ARIA software developers are in constant exchange with organizers of the WP3 OC, so that they can be made aware of specific needs arising from the calls in order to take them into account in their internal ARIA development plans.

Expectations are that direct and personal communication between applicant and technical experts before and during the application process will be crucial and the written application process will only be one building block of the overall application process. ARIA allows applicants to save proposals under construction and return to edit them at a later time point, so that the proposal can be iterated upon and improved before submission.

2.6. Open Call – User Project Evaluation

The selection procedure for Open Call projects should serve the main purpose of EOSC-Life WP3 – to contribute to the establishment of the Life Science cloud by supporting user projects that are typical use cases and therefore achieve maximum impact both for connecting the LS RIs to the cloud and for advancing scientific discovery. The selection procedure will therefore focus on the main aspects of impact and feasibility as well as necessary infrastructure.

Considering that the goal is to connect the LS RIs to the EOSC, any member of a RI is - in principle - in a position to identify suitable use cases that can advance the RI in its connectivity to the EOSC. Furthermore, we also welcome project proposals coming from external scientific groups or companies. Importantly, such projects should strive for close cooperation with at least one of the RIs and the topic must be of relevance for the Life Science community. For successful applicants not already affiliated with the RI in their field, contact to the select RI will be established after project acceptance by the WP3 Leads. Applications involving several RIs are encouraged as they help to improve interoperability across scientific disciplines, which is at the heart of cluster projects like EOSC-Life. These considerations also apply to the work with companies, which should operate in a field relevant to the LS RI community and which should clearly state the reciprocal benefit both sides can expect from such collaboration.

In the following we propose an evaluation process that is based on the experience gained through the current set of Demonstrators. It combines elements of consultation and evaluation, with the idea to define and then select projects with a high chance of success.

Consultation with applicants during proposal submission is an important part of the proposed selection process. Establishing a fixed deadline for final proposal submission, while working together with the applicants on potential improvements to the proposal based on feedback from OC and WP1/WP2 Leads before the submission deadline, will help to streamline the subsequent evaluation process and to generate project proposals better suited for the OC.

The evaluation will be a two-step process, with technical experts first judging the technical feasibility and secondly an external and independent review panel evaluating the impact of the

project. To make best use of expertise, the technical expert involved in the maturation phase for the individual projects should be the one evaluating technical feasibility at this stage.

For the technical evaluation, WP1/2/7 Leads are the first contact persons, but depending on the scientific field of the project, they can invite their internal WP experts in the respective field to participate in the evaluation process. There are two main cases to be considered:

1. If direct support is requested by the applicant, WP1/2/7 Leads also need to involve their WP experts to assess remaining capacity and to assign experts to work on the future projects (if successful), leveraging their experience gained in the alignment of experts to the first generation of demonstrators.
2. If project applicants want to work independently and request (mostly) financial resources to run the project, the technical evaluation should respect this and consider mostly if the team can be judged as skilled enough and equipped with the right set of expertise to conduct the project and if the project is technically feasible in the project timeframe.

Note that by engaging WP7 experts as integral members of the selection process, the WP7 Resource Allocation Process becomes part of the general evaluation process to avoid redundancies among different evaluation processes in different WPs.

Only project proposals that have passed the technical evaluation step successfully will be moved forward to the 2nd evaluation step, assessing their impact and scientific relevance. The EOSC Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB) is a body composed of scientific and ethical experts external to the EOSC-Life project designed to advise the consortium in scientific matters. In this capacity, the members of the SEAB were approached to take on the task of evaluating the OC proposals and assessing their impact for reaching the overarching goals of EOSC-Life. Additional experts can be invited on an ad-hoc basis, if proposal numbers are too high and would therefore exceed an acceptable workload for the SEAB or if further scientific expertise is required, which is not available among members of the SEAB. The impact assessment of the SEAB will provide guidance to select projects that e.g. bring large data sets of high relevance into the cloud, or establish workflows in the cloud that are regularly required by a large user base.

At this point, the applicant can still be contacted to clarify open questions if needed via the moderator.

Projects that are rated as technically feasible and of high impact will be prioritized according to their overall score. The eventual decision on how many projects will be accepted depends on available resources and capacity (see section 2.7) and will be supported by a WP3 moderator panel meeting. Open Call leads will communicate the evaluation outcome to the applicants at the latest eight weeks following the application deadline.

Evaluation criteria include the following:

1. Scientific excellence and impact
2. Potential to make available new valuable resources (data/services/methods) within the EOSC and for the scientific communities represented by the Life Science Research Infrastructures.
3. Feasibility of the project within the EOSC-Life runtime (the project must be completed and reported before February 2023 and start within 2 months after project acceptance).

4. Availability of resources within the project team: people power, computational & financial resources.
5. Availability of resources within the EOSC-Life technical expert teams: if EOSC-Life expert support is required in your project, please contact the relevant experts before submitting your project application to ensure that the requested assistance is available.
6. Sustainability after the end of EOSC-Life. Projects should have a clear plan for their sustainability beyond the duration of the funding period (e.g.: data/software/project output management plan).
7. For industry projects: level of reciprocal benefits for the company and EOSC-Life partners, potential for long-term collaboration

Review criteria for the scientific as well as strategic impact assessment by the SEAB were established by WP3⁷. Technical evaluation criteria for the technical feasibility check were suggested by WP3 and approved by the technical work packages (WP1, WP2 and WP7)⁸.

2.7. Open Call – Resource Assignment

To assure alignment with EU funding rules and goals, applicants are only eligible if they are associated with an institution eligible to receive EU funding⁹. Applicants can be affiliated with either academic institutions, research organisations, or industry.

The institutes of the WP3 co-leads hold a common pot for financing the support of selected Open Call projects. This pot amounts to 850,000 €, distributed across both institutes. This pot is supposed to be used for the support of about 9 - 12 user projects. As travel costs will be generally low, and as user projects in which partners are beneficiaries will use their existing travel budget, we earmark 10k for general travel costs across all user projects.

Thereby, if equally distributed, each project could benefit from about 70,000 € - 85,000 € for covering salary costs for experts working on the project. Note that these experts can be members of the consortium, but if only very limited support can be provided, and the applicants are expected to bring in the necessary expertise themselves, these resources will go to the new partners. Those new partners will be integrated into the project via contracts enabling the transfer of funds at pre-defined milestones during the project. Successful project applicants who are already part of the EOSC-Life consortium will sign Memorandum of Understanding (MoUs) that will outline the milestones of the project.

⁷ <https://instruct-eric.eu/network/eosc-life/eosclife-digital-life-sciences-open-call-reviewer-guidelines?t=eosclife>

⁸ <https://instruct-eric.eu/network/eosc-life/eosclife-digital-life-sciences-open-call-technical-evaluation-guidelines?t=eosclife>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register>

With this financial support, project partners can budget for approximately 12-15 person months on the project. Proposals should have a run time of 12 months from start to completion of planned work.

All given numbers are indicative only. Smaller proposals will also be considered and more funding may be possible for impactful projects. There may be differences among OC projects as a result of their prioritization and their planned achievements. Therefore, process, scope and budget to support the selected projects might vary on a case-by-case basis. The final decision on the resource assignment will be taken by the WP3 moderator panel consisting of all Open Call Leads and the WP3 Leads.

2.8. Open Call – Activities considered as out of scope

- 1) Novel dataset or workflow generation - the point of this Open Call is to make data and workflows available and not to generate them from scratch. Data and workflows should be available and accessible at the point of application
- 2) Large-scale data management-only activities - this Open Call should not replicate activities in a project's data management plan and should have a wide and demonstrable impact and use beyond a single project
- 3) Data curation of existing datasets - while improvements to datasets are in scope, provided they are newly accessible, this call is not intended to deliver curation resources for datasets
- 4) Workflows that cannot be automated - Human intervention should ideally be limited to steps upstream and/or downstream of the automatic part. Interactive work should be doable with computational notebooks or virtual desktops
- 5) Activities that are already funded by other sources. Care should be taken to differentiate applications to this Open Call from other funded projects
- 6) Proposals which only address the needs of an existing user base and do not have the potential to extend new functionality to additional users or communities

2.9. Open Call – Outreach and Communication

The selection of demonstrator projects during the grant writing phase of EOSC-Life exploited personal connections and existing affiliations to the participating LS RIs. However, the potential user base is much larger and the Open Calls should be advertised to a wider, external community to allow an open and unbiased selection process. Websites, social media channels, newsletters etc. from EOSC-Life and all participating RIs should be used to spread the information on the Open Calls to their respective user communities. Demonstrator projects can serve as exemplary success stories to illustrate the type of projects that can be accomplished and to make the concept behind EOSC more tangible. All Open Call Leads will support the development of such material and will adapt it to the degree necessary for their individual calls in close connection with WP10.

Nevertheless, it is foreseen that the complexity of the cloud environment and the lack of pre-existing knowledge thereof will not lead to many applications from individual scientists not

familiar with LS RIs. It may be key to address target groups individually and on a personal basis to encourage them to apply to the Open Call. Such target groups are e.g. scientists working in the thematic vicinity of LS RIs, users of LS RIs, contacts of ongoing demonstrator projects, companies of various Industry Boards, SMEs working in relevant fields and others. All submitters of project ideas to the market research (see point 2.2) will also be contacted directly to submit their project idea as formal proposal to the WP3 OC.

3. Next steps

Currently, the preparation of the first Open Call “Digital Life Sciences Open Call - A European Open Science Cloud (EOSC-Life) call for projects sharing data, tools and workflows in the cloud” is on its way. The Call launch is scheduled for September 2020. As WP3 has seen a high staff turn-over since the beginning of the year 2020, filling the capacity gaps will be crucial and the progress that can be made will be influenced by how fast new people can join WP3 and how knowledgeable they are in the LS RI landscape and in project management tasks.

Despite those uncertainties, the OC organizers are positive that the first OC can attract promising user projects that will help to shape EOSC for the Life Sciences and that will thereby support EOSC-Life in fulfilling its objectives in bringing new data resources and new workflows into the cloud. Streamlining and harmonizing work across disciplines by making cloud objects interoperable and reusable across a large scale of possible questions, applications and scientific domains has become even more crucial for society as demonstrated by the ongoing fight against the coronavirus disease.

Abbreviations

ARIA	Access to Research Infrastructure Administration
BSL	Biological Safety Level
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
IP	Intellectual Property
LS RI	Life Science Research Infrastructure
OC	Open Call
PM	Person Month
SME	Small/Medium-sized Enterprises
WP	Work Package

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed:

Yes

The deliverable has been delayed to correspond with the (postponed) opening of the first open call.

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

